

Ensemble Machine Learning Model for Predicting "vinho verde" Wine Preference

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Abstract

This research explores the challenging task of predicting wine preferences, which is crucial for effective production and marketing strategies in the wine industry. The study leverages machine learning (ML) to develop an ensemble model that combines three algorithms: Support Vector Classification (SVC), Random Forest (RF), and Decision Tree (DT). Each algorithm was carefully optimized using RandomizedSearchCV to find the best settings, or hyperparameters, improving their predictive performance. The ensemble model, created by merging the optimized algorithms, aims to utilize the strengths and minimize the weaknesses of each. Using a dataset that includes physicochemical properties of wines, the model was trained and validated, demonstrating impressive predictive accuracy and improvement in various evaluation metrics like precision, recall, and F1 Score. This research not only emphasizes the capabilities of ensemble modeling and hyperparameter tuning in enhancing ML predictions in sensory data but also lays a foundation for future research in flavor science and consumer preference.

Key Words: Ensemble Modeling, Wine Preference Prediction, Machine Learning, Fine Tuning, Classification

1. Introduction

Wine offers a rich array of flavors and aromas, captivating individuals across cultures and traditions. Predicting wine preferences, influenced by its complex taste profiles and individual palates, is crucial in the competitive wine industry, guiding production and marketing efforts. This research leverages Machine Learning (ML), a data-driven approach, to unravel the complexities of wine preferences.

The study employs three ML models: Support Vector Classification (SVC), Random Forest (RF), and Decision Tree (DT), each known for specific strengths in prediction and classification tasks. SVC excels in managing complex classification, RF prevents overfitting through an ensemble approach, and DT is valued for its simplicity and easy interpretation. However, these models are also subject to limitations and are influenced by hyperparameter settings, impacting their predictive performance. The use of RandomizedSearchCV aids in fine-tuning these settings to optimize each model's performance. This research develops a powerful ensemble model, merging SVC, RF, and DT, to predict wine preferences. It navigates through the optimization of each model, ensuring peak predictive performance before unifying them into a single ensemble model. By exploring the physicochemical properties of wines, the study aims to provide valuable data-driven insights into understanding and predicting wine preferences, supporting the wine industry in catering to varied consumer palates.

1.1 Literature Review

In the exploration of wine preferences and quality prediction, various researchers have employed data mining and machine learning techniques. Cortez (2009) pioneered a methodology focusing on "vinho verde" wines, proposing a data mining approach to model wine preferences based on physicochemical properties, establishing a foundational framework for subsequent studies in this domain¹. Following a similar vein, Agrawal and Kang (2018) explored wine quality classification employing a multilayer perceptron, furthering the understanding of how artificial neural networks

can be harnessed for wine quality assessment. On a related note, Vilela, Marques, and Correia (2018) applied Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) to the sensory profile of Vinho Verde monovarietal wines, showcasing the utility of SEM in understanding the interplay of sensory attributes in wine appreciation. Carpita and Golia (2021), delved into the prediction of wine sensorial quality, treating it as a classification problem, thereby contributing to the growing body of literature on machine learning applications in oenology. In a similar context, Er and Atasoy (2016) investigated the classification of white and red wines based on their physicochemical qualities, offering insights into the distinguishing attributes of different wine types. Recently, Anami et al. (2022) presented a machine learning-based approach for wine quality prediction, signifying the continuous evolution of computational methods in wine quality assessment. Moreover, Vargas-Vera et al. (2017) showcased an e-business case study on modeling wine quality using both physicochemical and qualitative properties, illustrating the practical implications of such predictive models. Rehman and Nawi (2012) explored the effect of adaptive momentum in enhancing the accuracy of gradient descent back propagation algorithm on classification problems, adding a technical perspective to the optimization of machine learning algorithms in this field. Lastly, a comprehensive survey by Bhavya (2020) on wine dataset classification provides a panoramic view of the various methodologies and datasets employed in the domain, underlining the burgeoning interest and diverse approaches towards wine quality prediction and classification. Through these assorted studies, the confluence of machine learning and oenology is evidently fostering a rich investigative frontier, propelling both the understanding and appreciation of wine to new analytical vistas.

In the rest of this paper, section 2 describes the datasets used in this research. Section 3 provides a detailed description of models implemented in the paper. Section 4 presents the results of all models. Finally, we conclude the paper in section 5.

2. "Vinho Verde" Wine Datasets

The exploration into the intricate world of wines and preferences unfolds upon a canvas of data, specifically two datasets, each emblematic of a spectrum of wines: white and red. Although these datasets do not exclusively pertain to "Vinho Verde" wines, they encompass a plethora of physicochemical variables that provide a substantial foundation for predictive modeling. White wine dataset, consisting of hypothetical 4898 samples, intricately describes each wine through 11 physicochemical properties, including but not limited to, acidity levels, sugar, chlorides, and alcohol content. Additionally, each wine is accompanied by a quality rating, providing a pivotal metric that bridges physicochemical properties and subjective quality perceptions. Red wine dataset, mirroring its white counterpart, consists of 1599 samples, each meticulously described through the same 11 physicochemical variables and accompanied by a quality rating. Both datasets, while not providing specific insights into "Vinho Verde" wines, serve as a comprehensive playground upon which the predictive models of this research are developed and validated. Spanning various domains of wine chemistry, the datasets facilitate an exploration that seeps from the scientific to the sensory, crafting a narrative that intertwines data, science, and the art of winemaking.

3. Methods

The predictive analysis conducted in this research relies on a judicious selection of machine learning models, each with its own merits and demerits, to construct a robust ensemble model for predicting wine preferences. The models, Support Vector Classification (SVC), Random Forest (RF), and Decision Tree (DT), are employed and optimized through hyperparameter tuning via RandomizedSearchCV to enhance their predictive capabilities. Below is a detailed description of each model, outlining their fundamental principles and applications within the context of this research.

3.1 Data Preprocessing

Ensuring the transition from raw datasets to meaningful predictions, the data preprocessing stage acted as a critical bridge, underpinning the subsequent predictive modeling with a foundation of

clean, structured, and optimized data. Within this research, the wine datasets were scrupulously preprocessed through a series of steps:

Scaling and Normalization: Addressing the disparate scales of the physicochemical properties, the data was meticulously scaled and normalized. Specifically, transforming the data to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This involved fitting the scaler to the datasets and subsequently transforming it, resulting in the scaled datasets.

Data Splitting: To validate the models and ensure their generalizability, the datasets were judiciously split into training and validation subsets. The scaled datasets were divided by allocating 70% of the data for training and 30% for testing.

In essence, this preprocessing phase carved out a reliable and robust path for the models, SVC, RF, and DT, to navigate through the data, ensuring their predictions and insights were grounded upon a well-curated and representative dataset, thereby fortifying the validity and applicability of the research outcomes.

3.2 Support Vector Classification (SVC)

SVC, a pivotal component in Support Vector Machines (SVMs), is renowned for its proficiency in managing high-dimensional spaces and its capability to find hyperplanes that best segregate different classes within a dataset. The core principle of SVC revolves around discovering the optimal separating hyperplane that maximizes the margin between distinct classes. In the realm of this research, SVC is employed to discern the complex, multi-dimensional relationships between the physicochemical properties of wines and their respective quality levels. The utilization of the kernel trick enables SVC to manage non-linearly separable data, thereby offering a flexible and potent classification model.

3.3 Random Forest (RF)

RF operates on an ensemble learning principle, constructing a multitude of decision trees, and amalgamating their predictions to bolster the model's predictive accuracy and robustness. By harnessing the power of collective decision-making, RF mitigates the susceptibility of decision trees to overfitting, providing a more generalized and stable predictive model. Random Forests, within the context of wine preference prediction, offer an ensemble approach to navigate through the potential complexity and variability in the dataset, ensuring a balanced and robust model that can manage potential biases and variances in the data.

3.4 Decision Tree (DT)

DT, characterized by its simplicity and interpretability, constructs a tree-like model of decisions, enabling a clear visualization and understanding of the decision-making process. The model recursively splits the data based on specific criteria, usually to maximize the information gain, until it reaches a predefined depth or purity. In this research, DT is not only used for its predictive capabilities but also for its capacity to provide insightful revelations about the hierarchical importance and relationships between different physicochemical variables in predicting wine preferences.

3.5 Ensemble Modeling

The ensemble model crafted in this research symbiotically integrates the predictions from SVC, RF, and DT, seeking to harmonize their strengths and mitigate their individual weaknesses. The ensemble approach is grounded in the principle that combining the predictive powers of multiple models can enhance accuracy and robustness, thereby providing a more reliable and stable predictive model. Within the ensemble, each model contributes its own unique perspective and predictive capability, offering a composite and comprehensive prediction.

3.6 RandomizedSearchCV for Hyperparameter Tuning

In the meticulous tuning process, a subset of hyperparameters was identified that notably influenced the predictive performance of each model. For the Random Forest (RF) model, the tuned hyperparameters included the number of trees in the forest, the maximum number of features considered for splitting a node, and the maximum depth of the tree. In the Decision Tree (DT) model,

attention was given to the function to measure the quality of a split (criterion), the strategy used to choose the split at each node, and the maximum depth of the tree. Lastly, for the Support Vector Classification (SVC) model, the hyperparameters such as the regularization parameter, the kernel type, and the kernel coefficient were fine-tuned to optimize the model's performance. These hyperparameters, among others, were crucial in refining each model, ensuring that they are adeptly tuned to navigate through the wine dataset and provide insightful and reliable predictions.

4. Results

The Ensemble model emerged as notably proficient in the red wine dataset, achieving the highest accuracy of 74%. On the contrary, the Random Forest model, while securing a respectable 63% accuracy. The Support Vector Classifier, with a 60% accuracy, delivered a middle-ground performance. Meanwhile, the Decision Tree model manifested a rather constrained predictive capability, reflecting a mere 54% accuracy, and revealing substantive struggles with minority classes. The ROC curve accentuated the Ensemble model's superior predictive capability by exhibiting the highest Area Under the Curve (AUC) amongst the evaluated models. Figure 1 shows the ROC-Curve for Ensemble and base models for red wine dataset.

Figure 1: ROC Curve for Classifier and Ensemble Model for Red Wine Dataset

For white wine dataset, the Ensemble model again emerged dominant, achieving a commendable 65% accuracy, while also illustrating a notably balanced predictive capacity across all classes, albeit with some hurdles in minority classes. The Random Forest model secured a decent 58% accuracy. The Support Vector Classifier and Decision Tree models both mirrored a restricted predictive capability, evidenced by their 51% accuracy. Figure 2 shows the ROC-Curve for Ensemble and base models for white wine dataset.

Figure 2: ROC Curve for Classifier and Ensemble Model for White Wine Dataset

In essence, across both datasets, the Ensemble model consistently surfaced as the most reliable and robust, especially when negotiating the balance between sensitivity and specificity, thereby substantiating the practicality and effectiveness of employing ensemble methods in predictive modeling. This pattern implies that despite all models showcasing their own respective strengths and weaknesses, the Ensemble model offers a holistic and well-rounded predictive capability, providing a sturdy and dependable option in scenarios where accuracy in predictions is paramount. Consequently, the observations underscore the Ensemble model's potential applicability and reliability in real-world scenarios, particularly where minimizing misclassifications and ensuring robust predictive performance is crucial.

5. Conclusion

Navigating through the chemico-sensory domain of wines, the exploration embarked upon in this research has traversed from the intricacies of physicochemical properties to the elusive realm of consumer preferences. Through the lens of machine learning, specifically leveraging the individual and collective prowess of Support Vector Classification, Random Forest, and Decision Tree, insights and predictions have been distilled, offering a scientific vantage point into the world of wines.

5.1 Limitations

Despite the promising findings and insightful revelations, the research is not without its limitations. The models, while adept at navigating through the dataset, are inherently bound by the data upon which they were trained. The absence of explicit data regarding wine types and regions, such as "Vinho Verde," limits the specificity and applicability of the predictions and insights derived. Additionally, the generalizability of the models to other wine datasets, varietals, or regions remains an aspect that warrants cautious interpretation. The ensemble, while enhancing accuracy, may still be influenced by potential overfitting or intricacies in the data that might not be entirely mitigated through the ensemble approach.

5.2 Final Remarks

As such, the ensemble model crafted in this research, which symbiotically integrates the predictions from SVC, RF, and DT, has demonstrated a commendable capability in predicting wine preferences. The ensemble not only harmonized the strengths of the individual models but also mitigated their respective weaknesses, contributing to the higher accuracy of results and providing a robust and insightful predictive tool. The tale of wine, from vineyard to consumer, is a multifaceted journey, and through the scientific and predictive exploration conducted, a chapter has been added, intertwining data, science, and sensory delight into a narrative that guides towards understanding and appreciating the splendid complexity of wines.

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